

SEVEN PERSONAL QUALITIES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHER AND LINKING SUPPORT WITH THEIR STUDENT

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Abstract

Luis – Fe Gomez (LFG) Diamantina National High School, where the researcher assigned as Practical Research and Language Teacher, Qualities of a teacher is one of the key arenas in the holistic development of the student. Burning its torch of discipline and excellence, the school believes that education plays a vital role in the development of human capital which is linked to individual's well – being and opportunities for better living. As far as the researcher observation there is a need in assessing their proper behavior because at their age critical changes in their intellectual and emotional growth. But, not all teachers are successful in building relationships with students. Five teachers who have been conferred with the 'Discipline and Excellence Test (DET)' in Senior High School Teacher of LFG-Diamantina National High School These DET test were selected as they are committed teachers who have consistently demonstrated outstanding performance over a long period of time with impactful achievements reflected in students' performance and in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form. One of the criteria for the DET was about their care and concern for students' needs in arranging learning activities to improve students' performance and development. The DET test shared good practices and memorable anecdotes with a focus on the strategies used in their classroom teaching as well as for building relationship with their students. The sharing was recorded and transcribed for analysis. Luis Fe Gomez Diamantina National High School served and believed in the motto #TayoParaSaMaunladNaDiamantinaNHS and center for Discipline and Excellence in the Division of Isabela where teacher has a vital role in teaching and learning process. From the Legal Bases of the teacher in Philippine constitution it was stated that Teachers are persons in authority when in lawful discharge of duties and responsibilities... shall therefore be accorded due respect and protection (Commonwealth Act No. 578) and Teachers shall be given opportunity to choose career alternatives for advancements.

Keywords: Seven Personal Qualities, Senior High School, Student, Linking Support.

INTRODUCTION

The study was conducted from August 2017- January 2018 for the Eight Personal Qualities of Senior High School Teacher and Linking Support in their Student of LUIS – FE GOMEZ (LFG) DIAMANTINA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL. There were 44 students of

LFG-Diamantina National High School who served as the respondents of the study. The descriptive method of research was employed and an instrument used to determine the impact of its problems. The researcher was personally administered a face to face interview. One of the main goals of the school is to promote discipline and excellence.

A positive teacher-student relationship would provide students with a safe and secure learning environment leading to an effective scaffolding of important social and academic skills (Hamre and Pianta, 2001; Baker et al., 2008; O'Connor et al., 2011).

A recent longitudinal study (Rudasill et.al, 2010) discovered that teacher-student relationship quality had close association with risky behaviors from childhood to early adolescence. A. Adapted from Importance of Philosophy of Education to the Teacher. B. Provides the teacher with basis for making his decision concerning his work. C. Help the teacher develop a wide range of interest, attitudes, and values concomitant to his professional life as teacher. D. Makes a teacher more aware of his own life and work, and makes him more dynamic, discriminating, critical and mentally alert. A good teacher-student relationship is important -leading to higher academic performance as well as better students' behaviors in classroom -students are more independent, cooperative and more engaged in learning (Birch and Ladd, 1997; Klem andConnell, 2004; Rimm-Kaufman and Sandilos, 2011).

Luis-Fe Gomez (LFG) Diamantina National High School, where the researcher assigned as Practical Research and Language Teacher, Qualities of a teacher is one of the key arenas in the holistic development of the student. Burning its torch of discipline and excellence, the school believes that education plays a vital role in the development of human capital which is linked to individuals well-being and opportunities for better living. As far as the researcher observation there is a need in assessing their proper behavior because at their age critical changes in their intellectual and emotional growth. But, not all teachers are successful in building relationships with students. This research aims to investigate whether those common characteristics of a good and effective teacher identified in some research findings are valid in the general academic strand and tech-voc for building a good teacher-student relationship, and to share some helpful practices for building such relationship.

METHODS

Five teachers who have been conferred with the 'Discipline and Excellence Test (DET)' in Senior High School Teacher of LFG-Diamantina National High School (namely Teacher A handle Math Subject, Teacher B Handle Science and Bread and Pastry, Teacher C handle Research and Language subject, Teacher D handle Language and Philosophy, Teacher E teaches Oral Communication and Personality Development) were invited to share good teaching practices in order to identify the personal qualities that are common to them for building a good teacher-student relationship. These DET test were selected as they are committed teachers who have consistently demonstrated outstanding performance over a long period of time with impactful achievements reflected in students' performance and in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form. One of the criteria for the DET was about their care and concern for students' needs in arranging learning activities to improve students' performance and

development. The DET test shared good practices and memorable anecdotes with a focus on the strategies used in their classroom teaching as well as for building relationship with their students. The sharing was recorded and transcribed for analysis. A qualitative approach was adopted by interpreting teachers' sharing of their good practices and memorable anecdotes. The analysis focused on their perspectives about how Diamantinnians teacher cope up with different diversity of the students and how they apply student and teacher relationships.

Apart from DET test 'sharing, students' views were also solicited in this study. A list of personal qualities was distributed to three classes of higher diploma students adapted from Cheng Winnie (2017) (a total of 44 students) to select and rank the first three pertaining to the outstanding characteristics of a good teacher. A total of eight personal qualities identified as common characteristics of a good and effective teacher in some research findings (Azer, 2005; Hui, 2003; Walker, 2008) were interpreted and listed out for students to rank. These common characteristics were 'coming to class with preparation', 'pagmamahal or showing warmth with care', 'understanding student's feeling with empathy', 'paghikayaat or encouraging students', 'Palatawang Guro or displaying a sense of humor and friendly smile', 'Patas or treating students fairly',. However, the findings and conclusions of this study could not be generalized to other institutions as this study is conducted with reference to the views of a limited sample of teachers and students.

RESULTS

The results of this study comprised of the following two parts:

Discipline and Excellence Test' Sharing

Diamantinians Senior High School strongly believed that teacher-student relationship had played an important role in their classroom teaching. Students actively participated in the research. They opined that a good teacher-student relationship enabled teachers to form positive bonds with students which helped develop a mutual trust, and give and take relationships. The following eight personal qualities were finally derived according to the traits commonly found in these DET test' sharing:

a. Committed to Work

All teachers demonstrated a professional and passionate attitude in their teaching philosophy. Teacher A and D tried to improve students' learning and accelerate their personal growth by engaging students effectively in drills and Outcomes-Based Education output. Teacher A and B strongly believed that a professional teacher who was punctual and well prepared for the lessons would deserve students' positive reinforcement. Teacher E made every effort to develop his student holistically and globally competitive Senior High School students. Teacher D significantly improved students' performance and development with a caring approach to cater for students' needs. Based on the result and finding it was clearly shown that students needs more attention and well just treated in their individual differences and just warmth and care to them.

b. Empathy

The Discipline and Excellence Test expressed their willingness to view things from students' perspectives so as to understand students' feelings and their needs. Teacher C shared his real life situation in achieving his goals in life to encourage his students to do the task as well. Teacher A is responsible and industrious stated that she had a practice of arranging personal talks with students periodically so as to listen to individual student's difficulties and concerns. Teacher B pointed out that she always watched out for students' facial expression, honest, and accurate. All teachers mentioned about taking students' needs and difficulties into consideration while designing their lessons.

c. Genuineness

Teacher E talked about his personal life and enthusiasm in exploring young people's interests such as their actively class, touching their lives and efficient teacher. Teacher A kept a student profile for tracking in their output particularly she is a family oriented. Teacher B strongly believed that discipline must show inside and outside

d. Open-mindedness

Teacher A and e pointed out that they never stereotyped their students and claimed that schema on young people with one's own values and beliefs would be a barrier to build a trusting relationship. Teacher C mentioned that he always appreciated students' views and prior experience. Teacher D stated that listening to students' views with an open mind was vital in achieving effective communication but idealistic view is shown on his principle in teaching.

e. Warmth with Care

Teacher A noted that students always seek for love and care. Therefore, she always talked to students with genuine warmth and treated them as friends. Likewise, Teacher C got a similar point of view because she noted that students in the GAS and Tech Voc class were mostly lack of confidence due to inferior academic background. Teacher B claimed that this is the most important personal quality for developing a good relationship with students. Teacher D always initiated counseling and mentoring with students about different topics. All teachers agreed that memorizing and calling students' names is a kind of gesture to show a caring attitude.

f. Respect

All teachers viewed this as a prominent personal quality on the grounds that a person could be motivated if he is appreciated, accepted and respected by others. They always believe in the saying that Respects begets Respect. Teachers C and E respected every student as a person with unique personality and experience. Teacher A stated that a teacher would receive the highest respect if one treated students with the highest respect. Teacher D believed that if students were well respected, they would develop a sense of belonging which would help reduce classroom tardiness, absenteeism and

promote student engagement in learning. Teacher B believed that this attitude was helpful in the early stage of cultivating a mutual trust between teacher and student.

g. Students' Ranking of Teacher's Personal Qualities

According to the response (100%) from 52 students, it was found that majority students (57.56%) ranked 'coming to class with preparation' as the most valued personal quality of a good teacher, followed by 'respect'(42.44%). 'Understanding student's feeling with empathy, and 'showing genuineness and treating students as friends' were equally ranked (33.55%) as the third outstanding characteristics. Overall, students' favourite personal qualities were also common traits identified from the Discipline and Excellence Test teachers.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Luis Fe Gomez Diamantina National High School served and believed in the motto #TayoParaSaMaunladNaDiamantinaNHS and center for Discipline and Excellence in the Division of Isabela where teacher has a vital role in teaching and learning process. From the Legal Bases of the teacher in Philippine constitution it was stated that *Teachers are persons in authority when in lawful discharge of duties and responsibilities... shall therefore be accorded due respect and protection (Commonwealth Act No. 578) and Teachers shall be given opportunity to choose career alternatives for advancements.* Researchers had identified different characteristics of a good and effective teacher that would improve teacher-student relationship. In a longitudinal, qualitative and quasi-research study of students in education, Walker (2008) formulated twelve characteristics of an effective teacher which were regarded as qualities of the most memorable teacher among these students. He stated that an effective teacher should come to class with preparation so as to actively engage students. A teacher's optimistic attitudes about teaching and students could appeal for students' praise and recognition. An effective teacher should challenge students with high expectations, be creative in teaching, and handle students and grading fairly. Other caring qualities, such as displaying a personal touch, cultivating a sense of belonging, being compassionate, having a sense of humor, showing respect to students, demonstrating the art of forgiveness, and admitting mistakes, were also valid characteristics that should be recognized by educators. Rimm-Kaufman and Sandilos (2011) opined that a great teacher should keep a positive attitude, show passion, engage students, understand students' interests, strength and weakness, and be open-mindedness. Likewise, similar personal qualities could be identified in other studies on the strategies to cultivate positive relationship with students. For instance, Pigford (2001) advised teachers to show interest in students, be warm and friendly, be observant and recognize students' problems, invite suggestions from students and so on. Azer (2005) pointed out that teachers should work with passion, encourage and appreciate diversity, create a climate of trust, interact and communicate respect and so on. Weakness, and be open-mindedness. Likewise, similar personal qualities could be identified in other studies on the strategies to cultivate positive relationship with students. For instance, Pigford (2001) advised teachers to show interest in students, be warm and friendly, be observant and recognize students' problems, invite suggestions from students and so on. Azer (2005) pointed out that teachers should work with passion, encourage and

appreciate diversity, create a climate of trust, interact and communicate respect and so on.

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